

Synthesis of 5,6-dihydropyran-2-one derivatives under coupled ultrasonication and phase transfer catalysed *in situ* generated ketene with chalcones[†]

Ragini Gupta^{*a}, Anshu Jain^a and Bindu Varshney^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Malaviya National Institute of Technology, Jaipur-302 017, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : guptaragini@yahoo.com; raginigupta@mnit.ac.in

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Modi Institute of Technology, Kota-324 007, Rajasthan, India

Manuscript received 28 January 2014, accepted 30 January 2014

Abstract : Various 4,6-diaryl-3-substituted-5,6-dihydropyran-2-ones (3a-f) were achieved in good to excellent yield by hetero-Diels-Alder reaction of 1,3-diaryl-prop-2-en-1-ones (1a-f) and *in situ* generated ketene/chloroketene/phenylketene using phase transfer catalysis (PTC) conditions under ultrasonication. In comparison to the conventional method, ultrasonic irradiation gave better yield in reduced reaction time. All the synthesized compounds were characterized on the basis of their elemental analyses and spectral data (IR, ¹H NMR and Mass).

Keywords : 4,6-Diaryl-3-substituted-5,6-dihydropyran-2-ones, 1,3-diphenyl-prop-2-en-1-ones, phase transfer catalysis, hetero-Diels-Alder reaction, ketenes, ultrasonication.

Introduction

Ultrasound assisted organic synthesis is a powerful technique which is being used more and more to introduce green concept in terms of energy conservation, waste minimization, easier manipulation, enhanced rate of reaction, extremely mild conditions and formation of purer compounds¹⁻⁷. Pyran-2-one derivatives are the building blocks in the field of synthetic and medicinal chemistry as a consequence of their interesting structural features and diverse pharmacological properties⁸ such as antifungals^{9,10}, anticonvulsants¹¹, antimicrobials^{12,13}, pheromones¹⁴, natural pigments¹⁵, antitumour agents¹⁶, plant growth regulators^{17,18}, HIV protease inhibitors¹⁹ and cardiotonics²⁰. This ring system is widely present in animal and plant kingdom where it is involved in different biological processes as biosynthetic intermediates and metabolites²¹. They have been used as starting material for a variety of synthetic approaches for preparation of heteroarenes, for example, Diels-Alder cycloaddition of pyran-2-ones with dienophiles gives bicyclic lactone cycloadducts, which are the starting material for the syn-

thesis of highly functionalised six membered rings found in natural products^{22,23}.

A perusal of literature revealed that there are many reported syntheses of 5,6-dihydropyran-2-ones, amongst them, the most common methodologies adopted are lactonisation of δ -hydroxyl acid derivatives²⁴ and oxidation of substituted dihydropyran derivatives²⁵. These two methods are quite inefficient as they involve several sequential steps and thus give poor yields. Feng *et al.* gave a more attractive methodology of their synthesis using hetero-Diels-Alder reaction of Brassard's diene with aldehyde, which gave the product in a single step²⁶, but reasonable yields have been achieved only with expensive Eu(hfc)₃, europium(III) tris[3-(heptafluoropropylhydroxymethylene)-*d*-camphorate]²⁷. In addition, diene itself requires careful handling and is unstable during storage. A comparatively stable resin bound derivative of Brassard's diene has been reported, but it too gave poor yields²⁸. Cyclocarbonylation of 3,4-allenols to form 5,6-dihydropyran-2-ones catalysed by ruthenium or PdCl₂ have been reported by Takahashi *et al.*²⁹ and Ma *et al.*³⁰ res-

[†]In honour of Professor K. C. Joshi on the occasion of his 88th birthday.

pectively; but the reactions came out with poor to moderate yields. Similarly, other published reports towards 5,6-dihydropyran-2-ones include reactions of ketene with α,β -unsaturated enones and ketoamides³¹⁻³⁴, which suffer from low yields and long reaction times.

Ketenes are the versatile substrates in organic synthesis which have been frequently reviewed owing to their cumulated double bond structure imparting a unique spectrum of reactivity³⁵⁻⁴⁰. There are many ways to synthesize ketenes from carboxylic anhydrides, diazoketones, ketene dimers, dioxinones, etc. through thermolytic and photolytic reactions⁴¹⁻⁴⁴. Although, from a synthetic standpoint these methods suffer from drawbacks, requiring cumbersome apparatus or tricky conditions⁴⁵⁻⁴⁸. In synthetic chemistry, they are more often produced from acid chlorides with tertiary amines, where alkylammonium salts produced, stay in equilibrium with free amine bases, making it difficult to drive the reaction to completion⁴⁹.

Keeping in view the above facts, there is a need for novel, simple, convenient and fast protocol for the synthesis of ketenes and this biologically important heterocycle. To the best of our knowledge, no attempt has been made to synthesize ketenes via coupled ultrasonication and liquid-liquid phase transfer catalysis yielding the title compounds (**3a-f**) in good yield. Our research group had

earlier reported various cycloaddition reactions and phase transfer catalysed reactions for synthesis of heterocycles⁵⁰⁻⁵³. Therefore, in a continuation to our endeavours towards development of green methodologies and synthesis of diverse heterocyclic compounds, we report herein the simple, convenient and mild phase transfer catalysed [4+2] enone-ketene cycloaddition reaction under ultrasonication leading to the synthesis of 4,6-diaryl-3-substituted-5,6-dihydropyran-2-ones (**3a-f**).

Results and discussion

1,3-Diphenyl-prop-2-en-1-ones (**1a-f**) were made to react with substituted ketene generated from acetyl chloride/chloroacetyl chloride/phenylacetyl chloride in the presence of *n*-TBAHSO₄ and KOH under conventional as well as ultrasonication in the hope of obtaining cyclobutanone derivatives by [2+2] cycloaddition but instead it was observed that 4,6-diaryl-3-substituted-5,6-dihydropyran-2-ones (**3a-f**) were obtained via [4+2] hetero-Diels-Alder cycloaddition (Scheme 1).

In the IR spectra of 1,3-diphenyl-prop-2-en-1-ones (**1a-f**) characteristic absorption peak due to >C=O group appear in the range of 1640–1625 cm⁻¹ which is downfield compared to normal >C=O stretching band. This downfield shift is due to extended conjugation of the carbo-

Scheme 1. Synthesis of 4,6-diaryl-3-substituted-5,6-dihydropyran-2-ones (**3a-f**).

nyl group with the olefinic double bond and aryl groups, which results in delocalization of the electron of carbonyl group giving ionic resonance structures. The olefinic double bond appears between 1620–1600 cm^{-1} . Ar-H stretching vibrations are observed in the region of 3040–3020 cm^{-1} . The strong bands at 750 cm^{-1} , 1230 cm^{-1} have been attributed to Ar-Cl and Ar-F stretching modes, respectively.

In the IR spectra of 4,6-diaryl-3-substituted-5,6-dihydropyran-2-ones (**3a-f**), aliphatic C-H stretching vibrations are observed from 2960–2940 cm^{-1} . Carbonyl stretching vibrations are obtained in the region from 1715–1700 cm^{-1} . The new band appears in the region 1230–1212 cm^{-1} is attributed to C-O-C stretching vibrations. Olefinic double bond observed between 1630–1620 cm^{-1} confirms the formation of pyranone. All other peaks remain unaltered.

In the ^1H NMR spectra of 1,3-diphenyl-prop-2-en-1-ones (**1a-f**) exhibit a complex splitting pattern. The two olefinic protons constitute an AB system and appear as a pair of doublets, the downfield doublet in the region δ 7.30–7.63 with coupling constant J 8.1–8.4 Hz is attributed to $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$ proton and the doublet in the region δ 6.97–7.1 with coupling constant J 8.1–8.4 Hz due to $-\text{CO}-\text{CH}-$ proton. This strong downfield shift of these two protons is due to extended conjugation with aromatic protons.

In the ^1H NMR spectra of 4,6-diaryl-3-substituted-5,6-dihydropyran-2-ones (**3a-f**) aromatic protons are observed as multiplet from δ 7.17–7.37. Two doublets in the region from δ 5.30–5.71 and δ 2.07–2.21 are attributed to $\text{CH}=\text{CH}$ proton and $\text{CH}-\text{CH}-\text{X}$ proton, respectively suggesting the possible formation of structure **3** and not **4**. Possibility of the product **5** can be ruled out by absence of any singlet in ^1H NMR spectrum expected due to presence of $>\text{C}=\text{CH}$ and asymmetric $\text{HC}-\text{X}$ protons. Doublet due to $\text{CH}=\text{CH}$ proton is in downfield since heteroatom is directly attached with $\text{C}=\text{C}$ and conjugated ring. Multiplet in the region from δ 4.09–4.23 is attributed to proton at C-4 position.

Finally, DART-MS spectra gave various peaks which showed an accurate molecular ion peaks at m/z 250 (**3a**), 284 (**3b**), 326 (**3c**), 284 (**3d**), 318 (**3e**) and 302 (**3f**) that agreed well with their corresponding molecular formulae.

A plausible mechanism for the formation of product **3** is outlined in Scheme 2.

Experimental

All the melting points were determined in open glass capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The IR spectra (ν_{max} in cm^{-1}) were recorded on FT IR model SHIMADZU-8400S grating infrared spectrophotometer in KBr pellets. ^1H NMR spectra were measured on JEOL-AL 300 spectrophotometer at 300 MHz and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded at 75 MHz using TMS as an internal standard (chemical shift in δ ppm) CDCl_3 was taken as a solvent. The IR and ^1H NMR were recorded at Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur. DART-MS spectra were recorded on JEOL-AccuTOF JMS-T100LC mass spectrometer having a DART (Direct Analyses in Real Time) source. The samples were subjected as such in front of DART source. Dry helium was used with 4 LPM flow rate for ionization at 350 $^\circ\text{C}$. Elentar Vario EL III automatic CHNS analyzer was used for elemental analyses. The DART mass spectra and CHNS analyses were recorded at Central Drug Research Institute (CDRI), Lucknow. Sonication was performed in a Elma S70 H (with a frequency of 37 KHz and operating at maximum power of 220 V). The purity of the compounds was checked by TLC using silica gel (60–120 mesh) as adsorbent, UV light or iodine accomplished visualization. All common reagents and solvents were used as obtained from commercial suppliers without further purification.

Method a : Conventional method :

A mixture of acetyl chloride (7.5 mmol, 0.58 g) and tetra-*n*-butylammonium hydrogensulphate (*n*-TBAHSO₄) (5 mmol, 1.69 g) in benzene (20 mL) was stirred at room temperature. To this, potassium hydroxide solution (50%, 10 mL) was added dropwise with constant stirring at 30–35 $^\circ\text{C}$ to generate ketene. After ten minutes, 1,3-diphenyl-prop-2-en-1-ones (5 mmol) (**1a-f**) in benzene (10 mL) was added dropwise with an interval of 10–10 min with continuous stirring at room temperature. The progress of reaction was monitored by TLC using hexane : ethyl acetate (90 : 10) as solvent system. After the completion of reaction the mixture was separated and benzene layer was washed well with water (3×5 mL), dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and filtered. Further purification was accomplished by column chromatography over

Scheme 2. Plausible mechanism of [4+2] cycloaddition of ketene and 1,3-diphenyl-prop-2-en-1-ones (**1a-f**).**Table 1.** Synthesis of 4,6-diaryl-3-substituted-5,6-dihydropyran-2-ones (**3a-f**)

Compd.	R	Y	X	Conventional method (a)		Ultrasonication (b)		M.p. (°C)
				Time (h)	Yield (%)	Time (min)	Yield (%)	
3a	4-H	4-H	H	1	86	25	92	290
3b	4-H	4-H	Cl	1.2	81	30	88	260
3c	4-H	4-H	C ₆ H ₅	1	83	20	89	322
3d	4-Cl	4-H	H	1.4	84	35	91	284
3e	4-Cl	4-H	Cl	1.3	82	30	87	319
3f	4-F	4-Cl	H	1	79	20	86	302

silica gel as stationary phase and solvents of increasing polarity are employed as mobile phase. Pure compounds (**3a-f**) were obtained in (hexane-ethyl acetate) (90 : 10).

Method b : Ultrasonication technique :

A mixture of *n*-TBAHSO₄ (5 mmol, 1.69 g) and KOH (5 mmol, 0.28 g) was ground together in a mortar. Then this mixture was transferred into a 100 mL round bottom flask. To this, acetylchloride (7.5 mmol, 0.58 g) in benzene (10 mL) was added dropwise to generate ketene. To

this, 1,3-diphenyl-prop-2-en-1-ones (**1a-f**) (5 mmol) in benzene (10 mL) was added and then further sonicated for the time period as indicated in Table 1. The bath temperature was maintained at 30 °C. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC. Sonication was continued until starting reactants disappeared as indicated by TLC. After the completion of the reaction, water was added and the mixture was extracted with CHCl₃ (3 × 5 mL), dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and filtered.

The filtrate was evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure. Further purification was accomplished by column chromatography using silica gel (60–120 mesh) as stationary phase and solvents of increasing polarity as mobile phase. Pure compounds (**3a-f**) were obtained in (hexane-ethyl acetate) (90 : 10).

3a : Yield (a) 86%, (b) 92%; m.p. 290 °C; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₄O₂ : C, 81.60; H, 5.60. Found : C, 81.67; H, 5.64; IR (KBr) : 3020 (aromatic C-H str.), 2940 (aliphatic C-H str.), 1700 (>C=O), 1630 (aromatic C=C str.), 1225 (C-O-C str.) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.29–7.37 (10H, m, Ar-H), 5.34 (1H, d, *J* 2.22 Hz, CH=CH), 4.09–4.16 (1H, m, CH=CH-CH-C₆H₅), 2.21 (2H, d, *J* 3.48 Hz, CH-CH₂); DART-MS : *m/z* 250/252.

3b : Yield (a) 81%, (b) 88%; m.p. 260 °C; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₃ClO₂ : C, 71.83; H, 4.58. Found : C, 71.89; H, 4.53; IR (KBr) : 3020 (aromatic C-H str.), 2950 (aliphatic C-H str.), 1705 (>C=O), 1620 (aromatic C=C str.), 1225 (C-O-C str.), 750 (C-Cl str.) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.21–7.31 (10H, m, Ar-H), 5.71 (1H, d, *J* 2.27 Hz, CH=CH), 4.15–4.20 (1H, m, CH=CH-CH-C₆H₅), 2.07 (1H, d, *J* 3.47 Hz, CH-CHCl); DART-MS : *m/z* 284/286.

3c : Yield (a) 83%, (b) 89%; m.p. 322 °C; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₃H₁₈O₂ : C, 84.66; H, 5.52. Found : C, 83.59; H, 5.49; IR (KBr) : 3030 (aromatic C-H str.), 2940 (aliphatic C-H str.), 1807 (>C=O), 1630 (aromatic C=C str.), 1215 (C-O-C str.) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.19–7.35 (15H, m, Ar-H), 5.40 (1H, d, *J* 2.58 Hz, CH=CH), 4.17–4.23 (1H, m, CH=CH-CH-C₆H₅), 2.07 (1H, d, *J* 3.48 Hz, CH-CH-C₆H₅); DART-MS : *m/z* 326/328.

3d : Yield (a) 84%, (b) 91%; m.p. 284 °C; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₃ClO₂ : C, 71.83; H, 4.58. Found : C, 71.81; H, 4.61; IR (KBr) : 3030 (aromatic C-H str.), 2950 (aliphatic C-H str.), 1710 (>C=O), 1630 (aromatic C=C str.), 1212 (C-O-C str.), 700 (C-Cl str.) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.17–7.29 (9H, m, Ar-H), 5.37 (1H, d, *J* 2.55 Hz, CH=CH), 4.12–4.15 (1H, m, CH=CH-CH-C₆H₄Cl), 2.24 (2H, d, *J* 3.66 Hz, CH-CH₂); DART-MS : *m/z* 284/286.

3e : Yield (a) 82%, (b) 87%; m.p. 319 °C; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₃Cl₂O₂ : C, 63.95; H, 3.76. Found : C,

63.92; H, 3.71; IR (KBr) : 3030 (aromatic C-H str.), 2945 (aliphatic C-H str.), 1712 (>C=O), 1630 (aromatic C=C str.), 1225 (C-O-C str.), 700 (C-Cl str.) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.20–7.30 (9H, m, Ar-H), 5.30 (1H, d, *J* 2.36 Hz, CH=CH), 4.12–4.15 (1H, m, CH=CH-CH-C₆H₄Cl), 2.24 (1H, d, *J* 3.66 Hz, CH-CHCl); DART-MS : *m/z* 318/320.

3f : Yield (a) 79%, (b) 86%; m.p. 302 °C; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₂ClFO₂ : C, 67.54; H, 3.97. Found : C, 67.57; H, 3.95; IR (KBr) : 3040 (aromatic C-H str.), 2960 (aliphatic C-H str.), 1715 (>C=O), 1630 (aromatic C=C str.), 1230 (C-F str.), 1225 (C-O-C str.), 700 (C-Cl str.) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.23–7.36 (9H, m, Ar-H), 5.34 (1H, d, *J* 2.36 Hz, CH=CH), 4.12–4.14 (1H, m, CH=CH-CH-C₆H₄F), 2.17 (1H, d, *J* 3.65 Hz, CH-CHCl); DART-MS : *m/z* 302/304.

Conclusion

In conclusion, hetero-Diels-Alder reaction between electronically rich ketenes and electronically poor enones is believed to take place via a two-step process. The first step is a nucleophilic attack of α,β-unsaturated ketones over the *sp*-hybridized carbon atom of the ketene to form a zwitterionic intermediate, whose disrotatory thermal electrocyclicization leads to the formation of corresponding 4,6-diaryl-3-substituted-5,6-dihydropyran-2-ones (**3a-f**) as depicted in Scheme 2.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Department of Science and Technology, Jaipur, Rajasthan for necessary funding and CDRI, Lucknow for providing elemental analyses and spectral data. Anshu Jain is thankful to Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR) for Senior Research Fellowship (SRF).

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